

18-20 April 2023

Workshop on Quantum-Chemical Methods for Strongly Correlated Systems

Venue: Institute of Physics at Lodz University of Technology campus in Łódź, Poland.
Building: B14, ul. Wólczańska 217/221, 93-005 Łódź Poland.

Understand the Potential of Strongly Correlated Materials with Theory & Practice

The aim of this workshop is to provide an in-depth exploration of the latest developments in electronic structure methods for strongly correlated systems. Our team of expert speakers and tutors will provide you with a comprehensive understanding of the subject through a combination of lectures and tutorials, paying special attention to high performance computing.

Discover the Power of Machine Learning

A separate session on machine learning will provide a unique opportunity to learn how to predict physical properties of the materials with the latest algorithms. With a focus on ultra-fast interpretable machine-learning potentials, this session is a must-attend for all scientists interested in cutting-edge machine learning techniques.

Hands-On Experience

Get hands-on experience using open-source TREX flagship codes such as:

NECI

**Quantum
Package**

**GMM
COR**

By the end of the workshop, you will have a deeper understanding of the theories implemented in these programs and the practical skills to use them in your own research.

Requirements

Basic knowledge of ab initio electronic structure methods is required.

Fee

There is no registration fee. Lunches and banquet are provided to all participants.

PROGRAMME

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